

EFFECTIVENESS OF CELEBRITY ENDORSEMENT IN ADVERTISING AND ITS INFLUENCE ON BRAND LOYALTY AMONG NIGERIAN CONSUMERS (A STUDY OF ENUGU URBAN RESIDENTS)

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Abstract

This study evaluates the effectiveness of celebrity endorsement in advertising and its influence on brand loyalty among Nigerian consumers, focusing on Enugu urban residents. The objectives of the study were to: determine the extent of use celebrities to advertise products in Enugu metropolis; ascertain the extent of exposure to celebrity advertising of products among the residents of Enugu metropolis; examine the effectiveness of celebrity endorsement in the advertising of products in Enugu metropolis; and find out whether celebrity endorsement is a potent tool to influence brand loyalty. The study is anchored on Cultivation theory and Consumer Choice Behaviour theory. The survey research method was employed for the execution of the study. A population of 1,185,169 was studied using a sample size of 400 which was determined using Australian Calculator. Findings revealed that there is high extent of use celebrities to advertise products in Enugu metropolis which is capable of influencing brand loyalty among consumers. The researcher recommended among others, that when selecting a celebrity advertiser, choose a celebrity who is not already strongly associated with a rival product or service.

Introduction

The dissemination of information regarding a product's availability, quality, and pricing is known as advertising. Advertising typically consists of a message conveyed with the goal of selling by influencing or planning for consumers to make a purchase (Oparaugo, Dogo Daji & Kawoh, 2020). Influencing consumers' purchasing habits and brand loyalty is the goal of advertising. Nonetheless, the goal of this essay is to examine advertising from the perspective of "communication and persuasion." If advertising is not compelling enough to draw in new clients and keep hold of current ones, advertisers wouldn't be spending millions of naira. Persuasion and product marketing are essential components of a successful advertising.

Today's society has been portrayed as one in which is enlivened with celebrities. This has made more brands deploy celebrities to differentiate their brand and to create an advantage when it comes to surviving in the market filled with other competition (Amenze & Nwokolo, 2024). Celebrities are treated as icons which make people want to live the lifestyle of their favourite celebrities. Endorsement as a channel through which a famous person such as political, soccer, movie, and music icon endorses a particular brand of product or service by using his or her status as a famous figure in society to convince the masses to patronize the brand's claims is a strategic adoption by most marketers and product managers in recent times (Idigo, Esione & Onuegbu, 2023). In recent times, companies are spending billions of naira per year in endorsing celebrities and repositioning their products in the minds of consumers by creating positive and good awareness of the products and brands (Ifeanyichukwu, 2016).

Celebrity endorsement is a pervasive marketing strategy used by companies worldwide to influence consumer behaviour and increase sales (Mazeli & Anyionu, 2025). Celebrity endorsements are one of the most prominent variables influencing purchasing decisions in today's consumer market (Oguntuase, Olasehinde & Ibikunle, 2024). The relationship between food and beverage products and celebrity impact is an intriguing topic of study in Nigeria. This introduction lays the groundwork for an in-depth analysis of "Celebrity Endorsement and the Marketing of Food and Beverages in Sokoto Metropolis," exploring the complex relationships that influence market dynamics, consumer behaviour, and brand perceptions. Companies all across the world utilize celebrity endorsements as a common marketing tactic to sway consumer behaviour and boost sales. This strategy entails well-known individuals using their notoriety and authority to endorse a good or service (Spry, Pappu, & Cornwell, 2011).

According to Omeje, Oparaugo, Anigbo and Chukwuka (2022), the use of celebrity endorsements as a communication tool has actually increased significantly in recent years and is now a worldwide phenomenon. Anyin and Ezema (2024) opine that celebrity endorsements have been shown to be an effective tool in this regard, as they can grab consumers' attention and help create positive associations with the product being advertised. As Agbo (2021) highlights, when consumers encounter multiple advertising messages across different media, celebrity endorsements stand out as a particularly effective way to create lasting impressions.

Celebrity endorsements have become a staple in Nigerian consumer goods advertising, especially for food and drink products (Oguntuase, Olasehinde & Ibikunle, 2024). Because of its diverse cultural tapestry and growing consumer market, Nigeria offers an intriguing backdrop for comprehending the complex relationship between celebrities and consumer behaviour. As consumerism and media access increase in the region, it is imperative to look into how this marketing strategy affects purchase decisions in Nigeria. It has long been known that celebrity endorsements are an effective marketing strategy that affects consumer behaviour in a variety of sectors (Erdogan, 1999). This marketing approach has become very popular in Nigeria in recent years, where celebrities have a big say in what people want to buy (Adeyanju & Olaleye, 2019). Marketers hoping to take advantage of the region's distinct customer dynamics must comprehend how celebrity endorsements affect food and beverage products in this particular geographic location.

The celebrity endorsement marketing approach has grown much more prominent with the quick rise of micro-blogging platforms (social media), such as Instagram, Twitter, LinkedIn, and Facebook, among others (Olaseinde & Aluko, n.d). Nowadays, brands use social media platforms to reach college-aged consumers (Burke, 2017). They also use celebrities as social media influencers, which is a relatively new marketing strategy in the era of social media known as influencer marketing. According to Dhanesh and Duthler (2019), influencers and celebrities are conceptually distinct. The celebrity endorsement marketing tactic has become much more prevalent with the rapid growth of micro-blogging platforms (social media), such as Instagram, Twitter, LinkedIn, and Facebook, among others. Brands are now using social media platforms to gain visibility in the college-age audience (Burke, 2017), while leveraging on celebrities as a social media influencer which represent a relatively new version of marketing tactic in the social media age called influencer marketing (Olaseinde & Aluko, n.d). This study, therefore, seeks to evaluate the effectiveness of celebrity endorsement in advertising and its influence on brand loyalty among Nigerian consumers, with a focus on Enugu urban residents.

Statement of the Problem

There is a growing trend in using celebrities to advertise produces, ideas, goods and services globally. From sports icons, to movie stars, to music crooners, as well as social media personalities. Many companies invest largely both in Naira and Dollars as well as other currencies to have big stars promote

their brands. However, what is not known is whether this advertising technique is as effective as it is perceived, and whether is capable of influencing brand loyalty. There is a recent upsurge in competitions in the Nigerian advertising space which has seen numerous brands use different celebrities to promote their brand across various media platforms. This study, therefore, seeks to evaluate the effectiveness of celebrity endorsement in advertising and its influence on brand loyalty among Nigerian consumers, with a focus on Enugu urban residents.

Objectives of the Study

The broad objective of the study is to evaluate the effectiveness of celebrity endorsement in advertising and its influence on brand loyalty among Nigerian consumers, with a focus on Enugu urban residents. The specific objectives of the study are to:

1. Determine the extent of use of celebrities to advertise products in Enugu metropolis.
2. Ascertain the extent of exposure to celebrity advertising of products among the residents of Enugu metropolis.
3. Examine the effectiveness of celebrity endorsement in the advertising of products in Enugu metropolis.
4. Find out whether celebrity endorsement is a potent tool to influence brand loyalty.

Research Questions

The following research questions guided the study:

1. What is the extent of use of celebrities to advertise products in Enugu metropolis?
2. What is the extent of exposure to celebrity advertising of products among the residents of Enugu metropolis?
3. Is celebrity endorsement effective in the advertising of products in Enugu metropolis?
4. Is celebrity endorsement a potent tool to influence brand loyalty?

Conceptual Review

Advertising is defined as a paid, non-personal form of publicity that promotes ideas, products, or services through mass media like visual, verbal, and text channels (Anyanwele, 2017). It aims to influence consumer behavior and perceptions towards a product or brand (Kotler et al., 2018). Advertising can leave a lasting impression on consumers, educating them about products and shaping their decisions over time (Anyin & Ezema, 2024). The content and delivery of the advertisement are crucial for achieving these goals (Royo-Vela, 2015).

Omeje and Oparaugo (2021) see advertising as all forms of print, electronic or online media messages written or spoken and paid for by a sponsor aimed at target audience with the objective of selling or marketing a product or services. Advertising is the communication of information about the price, quality and availability of a product. Generally, advertising involves a message communicated with the intention to sell by persuading consumers or intending consumers to buy (Oparaugo, Dogo Daji & Kawoh, 2020).

Advertising has been in existence for a long time but it came to a point when advertisers identified the fact that making use of famous personalities in ads actually improved the image of the brand or product and also create an alignment between the brand and their target audiences, making them connect as easy as possible (Amanze & Nwaokolo, 2024).

The practice of using celebrities in advertisements to promote products dates back to more than a hundred years globally but its practice in Nigeria can be traced to the early 90's (Ifeanyichukwu, 2016). Thus, we see famous Nollywood stars, football stars, basket ball stars, athletes etc., signing up with a particular brand by featuring in their advertisements on televisions, newspapers and billboards. For instance, Veteran actress Genevieve Nnaji was a Lux soap ambassador (Lux is a homecare product by the UNILEVER), Actress Chika Ike is also an ambassador for energy drink, Actress Funke Akindele popularly known as Jenifa is the face of Jobberman etc. Services industry are not left out as we see telecommunication networks in Nigeria signing up celebrities (actors, actresses, athletes, musicians) as their brand ambassadors. These ambassadors feature in the firms advertisements whether in the print media or electronic media. Nigeria has four major and dominant telecommunications networks and they are MTN, GLO, Etisalat and Airtel. MTN endorsed the likes of popular musician Davido, Tiwa Savage, Don Jazzy, Iyanya amongst others. Etisalat ambassadors includes controversial musicians like Seyi Shay, Olamide, Omawumi. MI, Flavour, Actor Francis Odega and actress Eniola Badamus. Airtel ambassadors includes top musician 2face Idibia, Phyno, Patoranking, Waje, rising comedian Akpororo and Big Brother Africa (BBA) host Ik Osakioduwa amongst others. GLO endorsed artistes like Veteran actress Patience Ozokwor (popularly called mama G), Funke Akindele, Ini Edo, Comedian AY, Helen Paul, Basket Mouth, Bovi, Actors like John Okafor (Mr Ibu), O.C Ukeje, Peter and Paul Okoye (P square) and others.

A Look at Some Celebrity-Endorsed Brands in Nigeria

Popular music star Phyno was signed by Guinness Nigeria for the “Made of Black” advert campaign between 2014 to 2016. Also, in 2020 till date, Guinness Nigeria has signed Big Brother Naija stars Laycon, Nengi and Prince in their new television commercials “Black Shines Brightest (Omeje, Oparaugo, Anigbo & Chukwuka, 2022).

Budweiser uses Big Brother Naija host and stars Ebuka Obi-Uchendu and Ozo in their television advertising. The brand also brought former football stars John Terry and Roberto Carlos to Nigeria for a match to promote the brand. This is in addition to using PSG and former Barca star Lionel Messi, Nigerian singer Teni and former Big Brother Naija housemate Mike. Beer giants Hero uses Phyno and Zoro in their adverts as celebrity endorsements and the duo even made a music for the beer brand. The brand also used popular music star Rude By (Paul of P-Square), music duo Umu Obiligbo and music star Ill Bliss and popular actor Nkem Owoh (Osuofia) and have recently added Big Brother Naij season six winner White Money.

Star brand have as well used Burna Boy as their brand ambassador as the Nigerian music star started gaining international recognition. Life lager beer uses music stars Flavour and Phyno in their adverts and the beer brand made an appearance in Larry Gaga's song “Egedege”. The “Life” brand also uses father and son Pete Edochie and Yul Edochi respectively, the first time a father and a son have appeared in the same commercial for a brand at the same time for celebrity endorsement.

Orijin beer have also used Big Brother Naija stars Laycon and Neo for their adverts. Tiger larger beer also uses DJ Cuppy, Noble Igwe, ShowDemCamp and Teddy A. Heineken lager beer uses Nigerian musician Jidenna for their television commercial. Trophy lager beer announced popular musicians 2baba, Falz and former Super Eagles captain Joseph Yobo as their brand ambassadors. Also, they used Big Brother Naija star Tacha and 2baba for their extra stout advert campaign.

Away from alcoholic beverage brands, Davido has endorsed Munch It chin-chin, Viva detergent, Infinix phone, as well as 1XBet. Also, Wizkid has been an ambassador of United Bank for Africa (UBA), the legendary Pete Edochie and Chika Okpala (aka Zebrudaya) have at different times endorsed malaria drugs. Super Eagles striker Victor Osimhen has appeared as a celebrity ambassador in a Moniepoint television commercial. Hafiz “Saka” Oyetero has endorsed both MTN and the defunct Etisalat. Burna

Boy is an ambassador for Sportybet, while legendary Super Eagles star, Jay Jay Okocha is an ambassador for Bet King.

Empirical Review

Arogundade (2022) examined how "*Celebrity Endorsement and Consumers' Purchase Intention of Brewery Products in Lagos Metropolis, Nigeria.*" There were four explanatory variables considered for the study in order to find out how celebrity endorsement will be perceived and they include celebrity attractiveness, trustworthiness, expertise and product match-up. The population of the study was thus 1,184. A census technique was employed for the study. The reason behind this is to prevent the possibility of high rate of non-response in the survey. The study anticipated some level of non-response since the products targeted have the potential to intoxicate consumers. The study revealed that celebrity attractiveness and celebrity expertise have positive and significant effects on consumers' purchase intention of Brewery alcoholic brands in Lagos metropolis up to the level of 0.774 ($p = 0.000 < 0.05$) and 0.172 ($p = 0.002 < 0.05$), respectively. Besides, celebrity trustworthiness and product matchup have a negative but non-significant effect on consumers' purchase intention of Brewery alcoholic brands in Lagos metropolis with the coefficient and probability values of -0.081 ($p = 0.185 > 0.05$) and -0.011 ($p = 0.809 > 0.05$), respectively. The study therefore implies among many others that the attractiveness of celebrities is also of great worth in the endorsement of a product because more customers will be persuaded by their meritorious qualities such as intellectual capacity, sportsmanship, and appeal.

Idigo et al (2023) examined "*Celebrity Endorsement and Consumer Choice of Product in Anambra State, Nigeria.*" The study had its scope concentrated on Onitsha local government Area of the State. This is because there are a number of consumer markets the city is hosting. The study adopted a survey research design and the population was 250 random consumers, and 207 questionnaires were received and used for the study. A structured questionnaire type of Likert was used in data gathering, which was face and content validated for validity and its reliability was established using Cronbach Alpha reliability test for internal consistency where an alpha level of .999 was achieved showing a good level of consistency. Data collected was analyzed using Mean, and Hypothesis testing was conducted using simple regression on Statistical packages for Social Science at 5% significance level. The findings reveal that, there is a positive effect of celebrity influence on customer conviction on patronage $r = 0.728$, $n = 207 - 1 = 206$ and $p = 0.25$. Thus, since p value is less than 0.05, therefore, there is significant influence of celebrity on customer belief on patronage of a product. Hence, the study recommended that, product or service management should adopt criteria for using celebrity endorsement if they wish to influence consumer choice of products

Oguntuase, Olasehinde and Ibikunle (2024) carried out a study on "*Assessing the Impact of Celebrity Endorsements on Consumers' Choices in Southwest Nigeria's Food and Beverage Sector.*" The study investigated the effectiveness of celebrity endorsements in impacting consumer's Choices in Southwest Nigeria's Food and Beverage Sector. This research took a quantitative survey method in examining data from the sample size of 300 Nigerian consumers that were randomly sampled in the South West subregion. Based on existing literature, the research examined key factors of effective celebrity endorsements like perceived authenticity, expertise, and brand-celebrity fit. The research also examined how consumer demographics and culture moderate endorsement effectiveness. Findings indicate that celebrity endorsements have limited influence on consumer attitudes toward food and beverages in Southwest Nigeria. Nevertheless, although celebrity endorsements can have a limited impact on the development of brand attitudes, their impact on long-term brand loyalty is not statistically significant in the Nigerian market. The research highlights the need for a more nuanced approach to celebrity endorsements, with a focus on authenticity, brand fit, and integration within an overall marketing campaign.

Olaseinde and Aluko (n.d) assessed "*Influence of Celebrity Endorsement on Consumer Brand Preference of Infinix Mobile Phones among Undergraduates of Select Tertiary Institutions in Osun State, Nigeria.*" The objectives of the study were to Investigate if celebrity endorsement has any effect on consumers' brand preference for Infinix Mobile Phones and; to ascertain if Information about celebrity endorsers has any effect on the purchasing decision of Infinix Mobile phones among undergraduates of select tertiary Institutions in Osun State, Companies can withdraw their endorsement from celebrities due to various scandals and this scandals can lead to people not patronizing the product due to the celebrity involved. The sample size consisted of 387 respondents who were randomly sampled from Adeleke University, Redeemers' University, and Osun State University, Osogbo campus undergraduates based on the Yamane formula. Questionnaire was used to collect data. Hypothesis one and two were tested respectively by applying the analysis of variance (ANOVA) and Pearson Product Moment Correlation (PPMC). Findings revealed that celebrity endorsement influences consumer brand preference of Infinix mobile phones and that news about celebrity endorsers also has an influence on the purchasing decision of Infinix Mobile phones among undergraduates of selected tertiary Institutions in Osun State, Nigeria. Nigerian celebrities have the persuasive influence to influence brand recall and even brand association which has a significant influence on brand preference most especially among undergraduates. Therefore, care must be taken to examine a celebrity's life and the individual's social acceptability at present before endorsement in order to avoid any negative image that could have a detrimental effect on brands, while still utilizing celebrity endorsements as a means of advertisement. This study adds to the literature on celebrity endorsement on consumer brand preference in relation to Infinix Mobile phone and its present celebrity endorser (Davido) that has not been studied.

Omeje, Oparaugo, Anigbo and Chukwuka (2022) "*Celebrity Endorsement and Consumer Choice of Alcoholic Beverages in Nigeria: A Review*" discussed the use of celebrities in adverts of alcoholic drinks. Empirical reviews reveal that the use of celebrities have been effective in adverts and sales of products. From the analysis, the researchers concluded that celebrities have added color to the power of advertising. In most instances, the use of celebrities in advertisements has created awareness of adverts and advertising campaigns for these companies and organizations' products and services, which has resulted in increased sales. It is indeed genius and continue to be a distinguishing feature or product recognition. It is a good omen in the advertisement industry around the world, and this paper finally recommends that this new development must continue recognizing these celebrities.

Oyeniya (2014) investigated "*Celebrity Endorsements and Product Performance; A Study of Nigerian Consumer Markets.*" The study objective is to determine whether there is any relationship between brand positioning, purchasing decision, brand equity and celebrity endorsement. Questionnaire survey of 142 respondents was used and analyzed with the aid of Structural Equation Model. It is evident from the findings that trust, level of expertise and celebrity-product fit positively affect product performance. It was, however, discovered that celebrity attractiveness and similarity between the celebrity and the receiver do not significantly affect product performance. Therefore, organisations which aim to use celebrity to promote their products need to take into consideration those qualities of the celebrities that will enhance the performance of the product.

Theoretical Review

The study is anchored on Cultivation theory and Consumer Choice Behaviour theory.

Cultivation Analysis theory:

Theory of cultivation (sometimes also referred to as the cultivation hypothesis or cultivation analysis) was a technique developed by Professor George Gerbner. He initiated the 'Cultural Indicators' project in the mid-1960s, in order to study whether and in what way watching television might influence viewers'

understanding of what the normal world is like. Cultivation research is in the 'effects' tradition. Cultivation theorists consider that television has long-term effects which are small, incremental, indirect but cumulative and significant.

Cultivation theory in its most basic form assumes that TV contributes to shaping, or 'cultivating' the view of social reality amongst the audience. The net effect of humongous television watching by audiences over time silently shapes social reality perception for the self and ultimately for our society. Gerbner argues that the mass media transfer existing attitudes and values in a culture: the media retain and keep intact such values in members of a culture and thus hold it together. He has argued that television has a tendency to impart middle-of-the-road political attitudes. Gerbner has also called this effect 'mainstreaming'. Cultivation theory distinguishes between 'first order' effects (beliefs concerning the everyday world, e.g. the amount of violence) and 'second order' effects (certain attitudes, e.g. towards law and order or safety). Two audiences for television are also distinguished: the heavy viewers and the light viewers. The focus is on 'heavy viewers'. Individuals who watch considerable amounts of television will be more affected by the manner in which television programs frame the world than lighter viewers, particularly when it comes to matters about which the viewer has limited first-hand knowledge. Lighter viewers might have greater information alternatives. 'Resonance' refers to the amplified impact on the audience where what individuals are watching on television is what they've lived through in reality. This double dose of the message on television is likely to increase the cultivation effect. This theory is nevertheless relevant to this study because it goes ahead to add that, residents of Enugu metropolis, who are heavily exposed to celebrity endorsements of products, are very likely to cultivate the habit of choosing those brands being endorsed by the celebrities.

Consumer Choice Behaviour Theory

Consumer choice theory relies on the assumption that individuals will make intelligent choices to fulfill their desires. They will try to select those goods which best fit their budget constraint, preferences, and get maximum satisfaction out of the options they exercise. Theory of consumer choice explains how the behaviour of a consumer is a result of the interaction between his income and preferences. Understanding this behaviour is essential to properly drawing the demand curve and determining the optimal price of a product. A customer won't simply purchase something because it's affordable; such an action would most likely never lead to satisfaction.

They'll instead purchase something which appeals to their tastes. The tastes guide how people spend money and time when alternatives are made available to them. Consumer choice is determined by both their budget constraint and their personal preference. Consumers may, on some occasions, have equal taste in two alternative ways and, hence, experience indifference. Similar to the budget line, the indifference curve shows various combinations of goods yielding the same satisfaction to the consumer. Consumer choice theory as a model of consumer consumption is significant since it can predict consumption patterns in the economy.

It is important to understand the determinants of consumer choice in order to explain the overall economic scenario. Consumer demand is a key driving force of economic activity, making it possible for money to flow in the economy. Demand curve indicates the relationship between the price of a good and the quantity consumer's desire at the price. As it is used in this study, the theory justifies the belief that the consumers of today in developed nations are far more concerned with how products are produced than they were half a century earlier. Consumerized nations of the last century have been beset by consumer behavior issues, particularly with regards to purchasing power, and there has been a focus on the key drivers of sales (Lusk, 2016; Meneses et al., 2014). Yet consumer attitudes in everyday life focus on concerns beyond these trends.

The increasingly globalizing markets and the greater processing along the product chain in modern societies have widened the knowledge gap and distance between producers and consumers (Princen, 1997; Weis, 2007). Consequently, the application of consumer choice theory to explain consumer demand provides firms with the means of setting up strategies for profit maximization and efficient management

of resources. This awareness of demand and its connection to personal budgets also assists businesses in creating the most advantageous price strategies for their products. Therefore, it is essential to understand customer behaviour in a bid to segment purchasing decisions as well as the various options in terms of product promotion (Hawkins et al., 2000). Consumer behaviour is applicable in various ways.

It first aids in refining marketing strategies. It secondly aids in the creation of public policy. Thirdly, it aids social marketing, which is selling ideas to customers rather than a product. A second benefit of emphasizing consumer behaviour is that it enhances the consumers themselves since consumer mindset comprises assumptions, emotions, and intentions to behave towards products in the marketing context. Such assumptions may be positive or negative. This theory suggests that the consumer choice behaviour of Enugu metropolis resident can be changed or influenced as a result of the celebrities they are exposed to in the advertising of products.

Methodology

The researcher used the survey research method for the study. A population of 1,185,169 was studied using a sample size of 400 which was determined using Australian Calculator. The researcher made use of cluster sampling technique. The instrument of data collection for this study is the questionnaire. Data for this study was collected from both primary and secondary sources. The primary data was through the administration of questionnaire.

Data Analysis

The data gathered from the field work of the study were analysed using simple percentage formula. Of the 400 copies of the questionnaire administered, 330 were completed and returned, hence, the analysis is based on 330.

Table 1: Extent of use celebrities to advertise products in Enugu metropolis

RQ1: What is the extent of use celebrities to advertise products in Enugu metropolis?

Variables	Frequency	Percentage
High	150	45.45%
Minimal	100	30.30%
None	30	9.09%
Can't say	50	15.15
Total	330	100%

Field Survey 2026

The table indicates that majority of the respondents (150 or 45.45%) of the respondents believe that to a high extent celebrities are used to advertise products in Enugu metropolis.

Table 2: Extent of exposure to celebrity advertising of products among the residents of Enugu metropolis

RQ2: What is the extent of exposure to celebrity advertising of products among the residents of Enugu metropolis?

Variables	Frequency	Percentage
Yes	215	65.15%
No	115	34.85%
Total	330	100%

Field Survey 2026

The table indicates that majority (215 or 65.15%) of the respondents are exposed to celebrity advertising of products.

Table 3: Effectiveness of celebrity endorsement in the advertising of products in Enugu metropolis

RQ3: Is celebrity endorsement effective in the advertising of products in Enugu metropolis?

Variables	Frequency	Percentage
Yes	250	75.75%
No	50	15.15%
Can't say	30	9.09%
Total	330	100%

Field Survey 2026

The table indicates that majority (250 or 75.75%) of the respondents believe that celebrity endorsement is effective in the advertising of products in Enugu metropolis.

Table 4: Celebrity endorsement capability of influencing brand loyalty

RQ4: Is celebrity endorsement capable of influencing brand loyalty?

Variables	Frequency	Percentage
Yes	200	60.61%
No	30	9.09%
Can't say	100	30.30%
Total	330	100%

Field Survey 2026

The table indicates that majority (200 or 60.61%) of the respondents are of the opinion that celebrity endorsement is capable of influencing brand loyalty.

Discussion of Results

To a high extent, celebrities are used to advertise products in Enugu metropolis. The practice of using celebrities in advertisements to promote products dates back to more than a hundred years globally but its practice in Nigeria can be traced to the early 90's (Ifeanyichukwu, 2016). Thus, we see famous Nollywood stars, football stars, basket ball stars, athletes etc signing up with a particular brand by featuring in their advertisements on televisions, newspapers and billboards. For instance, Veteran actress Genevieve Nnaji was a Lux soap ambassador (Lux is a homecare product by the UNILEVER), Actress Chika Ike is also an ambassador for energy drink, Actress Funke Akindele popularly known as Jenifa is the face of Jobberman etc. Services industry are not left out as we see telecommunication networks in Nigeria signing up celebrities (actors, actresses, athletes, musicians) as their brand ambassadors. There is high extent of exposure to celebrity advertising of products among the residents of Enugu metropolis. These ambassadors feature in the firms advertisements whether in the print media or electronic media. Nigeria has four major and dominant telecommunications networks and they are MTN, GLO, Etisalat and Airtel. MTN endorsed the likes of popular musician Davido, Tiwa Savage, Don Jazzy, Iyanya amongst others. Etisalat ambassadors includes controversial musicians like Seyi Shay, Olamide, Omawumi. MI, Flavour, Actor Francis Odega and actress Eniola Badamus. Airtel ambassadors includes top musician 2face Idibia, Phyno, Patoranking, Waje, rising comedian Akpororo and Big Brother Africa (BBA) host Ik Osakioduwa amongst others. GLO endorsed artistes like Veteran actress Patience Ozokwor (popularly called mama G), Funke Akindele, Ini Edo, Comedian AY, Helen Paul, Basket Mouth, Bovi, Actors like John Okafor (Mr Ibu), O.C Ukeje, Peter and Paul Okoye (P square) and others (Ifeanyichukwu, 2016). Celebrity endorsement is effective in the advertising of products in Enugu metropolis. Effectiveness of celebrity endorsement is a notion being examined by different empirical studies in line with brand related contexts. The content of endorsed message has been researched with brand evaluation and brand related perspectives. Research has shown that celebrity endorsement can help create a positive effect on the consumer's brand awareness, brand trust (Agrawal & Kamakura, 1995), brand preference (Kamins, Brand, Hoeke, & Moe, 1989), and purchase intentions (Ohanian, 1991). These endorser effects are

attributed to the celebrities' influence and their ability to transfer their values onto the brands they endorse.

Celebrity endorsement is a potent tool to influence brand loyalty. Typically, consumers have pre-defined attitude toward which celebrities they like and dislike based on the characteristics of credibility, expertise, trust, and attractiveness and decide which celebrities to use as persuasive tools in their advertisements. If the celebrity is well liked by the consumer, then the consumer will verify the celebrity as a source of credible information and in turn the endorsement creates a high degree of certainty and positive attitude for the consumer (Surana 2008).

Conclusion

From the findings of the study, the researcher concludes that celebrities are used to advertise products and this is to a high extent. Also, the residents of Enugu metropolis are highly exposed to these celebrity advertising of products by brands. Celebrity endorsement is effective in the advertising of products as affirmed by the residents of Enugu metropolis. Celebrity endorsement is a potent tool to influence brand loyalty, as most consumers seem to switch or maintain using a product if their favourite superstar identifies or endorses the product.

Recommendations

The following recommendations are made based on the findings of the study:

- i. Celebrity advertising will be ineffective when used consistently over time to increase the strength of the link between the celebrity and the endorsed brand;
- ii. When using a celebrity advertiser, keep the advertisement execution simple, clean, and free of irrelevant design elements;
- iii. When selecting a celebrity advertiser, choose a celebrity who is not already strongly associated with a rival product or service;
- iv. When selecting a celebrity advertiser, consider carefully the "fit", "congruence", or "belongingness" of the celebrity and brand.

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